

Improving Timely Access and Continuity of Care in a Community Health Clinic

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Background

Timely access to care improves health outcomes
Continuity of care = reduced mortality and costs
Affordable Care Act increased number of insured during a shortage of primary care providers (PCP)
PCP shortage increased in medically underserved communities
Prolonged wait times contribute to poor continuity of care and worse health outcomes for the poor

Aim

Develop a business plan for a new federally qualified health center (FQHC) in Central New Mexico to optimize timely access and continuity of care

Sandoval County, New Mexico

Population ≈145,179
15.3% living in poverty
16.7% Spanish as primary language
12 Native American Reservations
Medically underserved area
31.9% Medicaid (22.7% US average)
Two hospitals in the county

- Non-profit
- Satellite hospital for the University of New Mexico

Measures

Number of days until the 3rd next available appointment
Daily % of patients seen and empaneled to PCP
Daily # of open access PCP appointments
Daily # of appointment requests for PCP
Hourly # of patients seen by PCP
Monthly # of PCP empaneled patients

Theoretical Framework: Six Sigma Model

Fictional Control Charts Procedures

New Mexico's Human Services Department criteria for timely access:

- Urgent & symptomatic appointments seen within 24 hours
- Routine asymptomatic appointment seen within 30 days

PCP Staffing:

- 6 providers: Monday through Friday with varying hours
- 21 open appointments/day
- 20 minutes in length
- 1 hour administrative time/day
- 40 minutes allotted per Emergency Room follow-ups (2/day)
- 5 hospital follow-ups/week (1/day)
- 1 appointment/day for new patients
- Open Access: Half of daily PCP appointments saved for the day of the request

Business Plan

Assets:
Health Resources and Services Administration Grant \$1,000,000 for new healthcare site in high need area
New Mexico's Medicaid reimburses average \$660 per member per month

- 12,000 patients
- 24 staff members
- 6 medical providers
- 2 medical assistants per provider
- 1 each: health educator/administrative/clinic manager/dietitian/clinic supervisor
- 3 front desk clerks
- 2 each: case managers, registered nurses

Fixed Assets:

- \$87,000 office & exam room equipment

Total assets: \$9,107,000

Liabilities:
FQHC contributes 25% towards employees benefits: \$451,625
Income tax payable: \$3,956,910
Office equipment and supplies: \$8,000
Mortgage lease payable: \$300,000

Total liabilities: \$9,106,895

Discussion

More Full Time Equivalents supporting PCPs
Scheduling based on potential patient needs
Future iterations:

- Improve the no-show rate
- Add pharmacy and pharmacist
- Add collaborative billable visits for nurses, dietitian, health educator, pharmacist
- Assess patient satisfaction and patients suggestions for improved care
- Future iterations in scheduling